

Cation Exchange Separation of Metal Ions in Aqueous Sodium Glycollate Media

M. SITA RAMA REDDY, ANIMESH K. GHOSE*

Chemical Laboratories, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002

and

LALIT C. T. EUSEBIUS

Department of Chemistry, Ewing Christian College, Allahabad-211 003

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The cation exchange behaviour of 20 cations has been studied on strongly acidic Amberlite IR-120 (20-50 mesh, 8-10% cross linkage, Na⁺ form) in aqueous sodium glycollate media. The distribution coefficients (*K*) determined through batch technique revealed the possibilities of a number of separations. The actual separations of metal ions were obtained on a short resin column of ~7.5 cm height. The ternary separations were also achieved on ~10 cm long resin column.

The distribution coefficients (*K*), column elution behaviour, elution curves and results of some of the binary and ternary cation mixtures along with standard deviations are presented.

THE use of complexing agents has tremendously increased the application of ion-exchange chromatography. For obtaining a specific separation the ion-exchange equilibria can suitably be adjusted with the help of complexants. Sodium glycollate has pronounced complexation tendency and many metal glycollates are known¹⁻³. A systematic cation exchange study of metal ions in α -hydroxyisobutyric acid with alcohols was reported⁴. No information is available on the use of sodium glycollate in the ion-exchange chromatography. Therefore, the present investigation was undertaken to study the distribution coefficients of a number of metal ions in 0.04-0.40 mol dm⁻³ aqueous sodium glycollate, the elution behaviour, and the results of resolution of synthetic binary and ternary mixtures along with standard deviations are presented in this paper.

Experimental

Materials: Purified strongly acidic cation exchanger Amberlite IR-120 (20-50 mesh, 8-10% cross-linked, Na⁺ form) was used for both batch and column studies. The resin capacity and its water contents were ~2.85 meq/g and ~35%, respectively.

Fresh 0.05 to 0.20 mol dm⁻³ solutions of Mg^{II}, Al^{III}, Ca^{II}, Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Sr^{II}, Cd^{II}, Ba^{II}, La^{III}, Ce^{III}, Pb^{II} and Th^{IV} were prepared from their reagent grade nitrate (AnalaR or Johnson Mathey). Fe^{III}, Ga^{III}, In^{III} and Hg^{II} solutions were prepared directly in sodium glycollate solution from their nitrate. Aqueous 1.0 mol dm⁻³ solution of sodium glycollate (Fluka AG Buchs SG) was used. Wash solutions were 0.04-0.20 mol dm⁻³ aqueous sodium glycollate as the case may be.

Procedure :

Distribution coefficients (*K*): The batch technique was employed for the determination of distribution coefficients. Air dried resin (1 g) was added to a constant amount of metal ion and varying amounts (0.04 to 0.40 mol dm⁻³) of sodium glycollate solution. The overall volume was kept at 25 cm³. The solutions were mechanically shaken in wrist motion microid flask shakers (Griffin & George Co.) for 1 h and then filtered to separate the resin. The metal ion content were determined complexometrically⁵⁻⁸ in the solution phase. The distribution coefficient (*K*) was determined by using the relationship, $K = \text{mg metal ion per g resin} / \text{mg metal ion per cm}^3 \text{ solution}$.

All experiments were conducted in duplicate at 30 ± 2°. The values of *K* are presented in Table 1. The experimental error was found to be less than ± 5%.

Column chromatographic studies: The following method was used for the resolution of binary and ternary mixtures. Fully water swollen resin slurry (~5 g) was transferred to the graduated chromatographic column to a height of ~7.5 cm. It was washed with various washing solutions as the case may be. The 25 cm³ of the feed containing metal ions to be separated, was prepared in duplicate in 0.04/0.12/0.20 mol dm⁻³ aqueous sodium glycollate solution. The feed was passed through the preconditioned column at a flow rate of 1.0 ± 0.3 cm³ min⁻¹. The effluent was collected from the beginning of sorption step unless otherwise mentioned. The most weakly sorbed metal ions often followed the effluent and were quantitatively recovered with 0.04-0.20 mol dm⁻³ sodium glycollate eluent. The

TABLE 1—DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS (*K*) IN AQUEOUS SODIUM GLYCOLLATE

Metal ion	Distribution coefficient (<i>K</i>)				
	Concentration of sodium glycollate, mol dm ⁻³				
	0.04	0.12	0.20	0.28	0.40
Mg ^{II}	475	144	41	32	14
Al ^{III}	110	12	10	2	1
Ca ^{II}	475	145	41	32	15
Cr ^{III}	75	13	8	1	1
Mn ^{II}	475	113	37	20	9
Fe ^{III}	37	4	3	2	1
Co ^{II}	133	37	11	2	1
Ni ^{II}	212	34	11	6	1
Cu ^{II}	75	8	5	1	1
Zn ^{II}	10 ⁴	30	8	2	1
Ga ^{III}	45	6	4	2	1
Sr ^{II}	10 ⁴	141	100	58	37
Cd ^{II}	465	56	15	3	1
In ^{III}	325	8	6	4	1
Ba ^{II}	10 ⁴	475	225	167	114
La ^{III}	10 ⁴	275	58	17	3
Ce ^{III}	10 ⁴	151	22	11	1
Hg ^{II}	3	2	1	1	1
Pb ^{II}	475	75	30	13	6
Th ^{IV}	141	17	8	3	1

strongly sorbed metal ions were either desorbed with higher concentrations of sodium glycollate solutions or with any other suitable eluent.

Results and Discussion

The distribution coefficient values presented in Table 1 show that the affinity of almost all metal ions decrease with increase of concentration of sodium glycollate. This decrease of *K* values is due to the complexation of metal ions with glycollate resulting in the formation of either neutral or low positively charged metal-ligand species. As the concentration of glycollate ion is further increased the number of neutral or low positively charged species also increases thereby causing further decrease in the *K* values. The very low *K* values of Hg^{II} from 0.04 to 0.40 mol dm⁻³ suggest the formation of either large number of neutral species having very low dissociation or negatively charged species.

Prediction of separation possibilities : The very low *K* values (~3) of Hg^{II} at 0.04 mol dm⁻³ sodium glycollate indicate its separation from all other metal ions. Hg^{II} follows the effluent and therefore, effluent is collected from the beginning of the sorption step. It can easily be quantitatively recovered with 0.04 mol dm⁻³ sodium glycollate eluent while the other strongly sorbed metal ions may be eluted either with 0.40 mol dm⁻³ sodium glycollate or with mineral acids.

At 0.12 mol dm⁻³ sodium glycollate the *K* values of Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ga^{III} and In^{III} are sufficiently low to allow their separation from Mg^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II}, Sr^{II}, Cd^{II}, Ba^{II}, La^{III}, Ce^{III} and Pb^{II} metal ions having sufficiently high *K* values. Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ga^{III} and In^{III} can be recovered first with 0.12 mol dm⁻³ sodium glycollate eluent followed by elution of other strongly retained metal ions either with 0.40 mol dm⁻³ sodium glycollate or mineral acids.

Th^{IV} has *K* value 8 at 0.20 mol dm⁻³ sodium glycollate medium and can be separated from other metal ions Mn^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II}, Ba^{II}, La^{III} and Ce^{III} having sufficiently high *K* values to be retained onto the resin bed. Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} can be separated from other metal ions in 0.40 mol dm⁻³ sodium glycollate medium. Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} are strongly sorbed due to high *K* values whereas other metal ions sorbed weakly and therefore, can be eluted with 0.40 mol dm⁻³ sodium glycollate eluent.

On the basis of possibilities of various binary separations a number of ternary separations are also predicted. All the binary and ternary separations thus predicted are presented in Table 2.

Separation on column : A large number of binary and ternary separations were achieved through column chromatography, but a few separations are being discussed here.

Binary separations : Hg^{II} from all other metal ions was separated with feed prepared in 0.04 mol dm⁻³ aqueous sodium glycollate. Hg^{II} was detected even in the effluent and therefore, the effluent was collected, in 5 ml fractions, from the beginning of sorption step. The whole of Hg^{II} was recovered with ~60 cm³ of 0.04 mol dm⁻³ sodium glycollate as eluent. The strongly retained metal ions were desorbed with 0.40 mol dm⁻³ sodium glycollate solution except Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} which were

TABLE 2—POSSIBLE BINARY AND TERNARY SEPARATIONS OF METAL IONS IN AQUEOUS SODIUM GLYCOLLATE MEDIA

Sl. no.	Binary Separation	
	First component eluted	Second component eluted
1.	Hg ^{II}	All other metal ions
2.	Fe ^{III} , Cu ^{II} , Ga ^{III} , In ^{III}	Mn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Mg ^{II} , Ca ^{II} , Sr ^{II} , Ba ^{II} , La ^{III} , Ce ^{III} , Pb ^{II}
3.	Al ^{III} , Th ^{IV}	Mn ^{II} , Mg ^{II} , Ca ^{II} , Sr ^{II} , Ba ^{II} , La ^{III} , Ce ^{III} , Pb ^{II}
4.	Th ^{IV}	Mn ^{II} , Mg ^{II} , Ca ^{II} , Sr ^{II} , Ba ^{II} , La ^{III} , Ce ^{III} , Pb ^{II}
5.	Al ^{III} , Cr ^{III} , Zn ^{II}	Sr ^{II} , Ba ^{II} , Pb ^{II}
6.	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cd ^{II}	Sr ^{II} , Ba ^{II} , La ^{III}
7.	Mg ^{II} , Ca ^{II} , Sr ^{II} , Ba ^{II}	Al ^{III} , Cr ^{III} , Fe ^{III} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Ga ^{III} , In ^{III} , Cd ^{II} , Hg ^{II} , Th ^{IV}
8.	Mn ^{II} , La ^{III} , Ce ^{III} , Pb ^{II}	Sr ^{II} , Pb ^{II}
9.	Mg ^{II} , Ca ^{II}	Ba ^{II}
10.	Sr ^{II} , Ba ^{II}	Other metal ions

(Table 2 contd.)

Ternary Separation		
First component eluted	Second component eluted	Third component eluted
1. Hg ^{II}	Fe ^{III} , Cu ^{II} , Ga ^{III} , In ^{III}	Mn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Mg ^{II} , Ca ^{II} , Sr ^{II} , Ba ^{II} , La ^{III} , Ce ^{III} , Pb ^{II}
2. Hg ^{II}	Th ^{IV}	Mn ^{II} , Mg ^{II} , Ca ^{II} , Sr ^{II} , Ba ^{II} , La ^{III} , Ce ^{III}
3. Hg ^{II}	Al ^{III} , Cr ^{III} , Zn ^{II}	Sr ^{II} , Ba ^{II} , La ^{III} , Ce ^{III}
4. Fe ^{III} , Cu ^{II} , Ga ^{III} , In ^{III}	Mn ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , La ^{III} , Ce ^{III} , Pb ^{II}	Sr ^{II} , Ba ^{II}
5. Al ^{III} , Cr ^{III}	Mg ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Mn ^{II} , La ^{III} , Ce ^{III} , Pb ^{II}	Sr ^{II} , Ba ^{II}
6. Th ^{IV}	Ca ^{II} , Mg ^{II} , La ^{III} , Ce ^{III} , Pb ^{II}	Sr ^{II} , Ba ^{II}
7. Ga ^{III} , In ^{III} , Fe ^{III} , Cu ^{II}	Ni ^{II} , Co ^{II}	Ca ^{II} , Sr ^{II} , Ba ^{II} , La ^{III} , Ce ^{III}

eluted with 4.0 mol dm⁻³ HCl. The results of separations are reported in Table 4.

Fe^{III}/Cu^{II}/Ga^{III} or In^{III} from Mn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II}, Ba^{II}, Pb^{II}, La^{III} or Ce^{III} separation feed was prepared in 0.12 mol dm⁻³ sodium glycollate solution. Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ga^{III} or In^{III} were recovered first quantitatively with 0.12 mol dm⁻³ sodium

TABLE 3—ELUTION CHARACTERISTICS OF METAL IONS ON AMBERLITE IR-120 IN SODIUM GLYCOLLATE

Metal ion	BTV cm ³	VEP cm ³	TEV cm ³	Eluent (Na-glycollate) mol dm ⁻³
Hg ^{II}	5	30	60	0.04
Ga ^{III}	0	30	40	0.12
In ^{III}	10	40	70	0.12
Fe ^{III}	5	30	40	0.12
Cu ^{II}	5	30	90	0.12
Ni ^{II}	0	50	110	0.20
Co ^{II}	25	130	220	0.30
Cd ^{II}	45	155	245	0.30
Zn ^{II}	15	75	125	0.30
Al ^{III}	40	60	90	0.30
Cr ^{III}	10	40	90	0.30
Th ^{IV}	25	45	95	0.30
Ce ^{III}	40	100	120	0.30
La ^{III}	0	30	60	0.40
Mn ^{II}	0	60	110	0.40
Pb ^{II}	10	50	90	0.40
Ce ^{III}	0	25	50	0.40

glycollate eluent. The elution characteristics of these metal ions are presented in Table 3. Then the strongly retained metal ions were eluted with either 0.40 mol dm⁻³ sodium glycollate or with mineral acid. The results of separation along with standard deviations are presented in Table 4.

TABLE 4—RESULTS OF RESOLUTION OF BINARY MIXTURES

Metal ions	Taken		Found		Eluent
	Mean amount mg	Mean amount mg	Number of determinations	Standard deviation	
1st. constituent eluted					
Hg ^{II}	106.58	105.25	36	±0.20	A
Fe ^{III}	24.57	24.60	18	±0.12	B
Cu ^{II}	33.52	33.70	18	±0.14	B
Ga ^{III}	23.13	23.00	18	±0.12	B
In ^{III}	25.47	25.25	18	±0.04	B
Th ^{IV}	80.62	80.20	16	±0.06	C
2nd. constituent eluted					
Mg ^{II}	11.80	11.92	12	±0.14	D
Al ^{III}	9.35	9.15	02	±0.10	E
Ca ^{II}	20.25	20.20	12	±0.06	D
Cr ^{III}	15.38	15.48	02	±0.05	E
Mn ^{II}	31.28	31.40	12	±0.11	E
Fe ^{III}	21.05	21.20	02	±0.12	E
Co ^{II}	30.82	30.60	02	±0.09	E
Ni ^{II}	31.68	31.50	02	±0.10	E
Cu ^{II}	33.52	33.70	02	±0.12	E
Zn ^{II}	31.23	31.10	02	±0.12	E
Ga ^{III}	23.13	22.00	02	±0.08	E
Sr ^{II}	43.00	42.80	12	±0.15	D
Cd ^{II}	52.24	52.00	10	±0.20	E
In ^{III}	26.65	26.85	02	±0.16	E
Ba ^{II}	65.15	65.40	12	±0.22	D
La ^{III}	48.06	48.26	12	±0.16	E
Ce ^{III}	35.72	35.98	12	±0.12	E
Pb ^{II}	102.12	102.92	12	±0.30	E
Th ^{IV}	82.32	82.62	02	±0.22	E

A=0.04 mol dm⁻³ Na-glycollate.
 B=0.12 mol dm⁻³ Na-glycollate.
 C=0.20 mol dm⁻³ Na-glycollate.
 D=0.40 mol dm⁻³ Na-glycollate.
 E=4.00 mol dm⁻³ HCl.

Th^{IV} from Mn^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II}, Ba^{II}, Pb^{II}, La^{III} or Ce^{III} was separated from 0.20 mol dm⁻³ sodium glycollate solution. Th^{IV} was first eluted with 0.20 mol dm⁻³ sodium glycollate eluent. The breakthrough of Th^{IV} was at 25 cm³ and the total elution volume ~95 cm³. The strongly sorbed other metal ions were subsequently stripped off as described earlier. The results of these separations with standard deviations are presented in Table 4. Fig. 1 shows elution curve for the separation of Th^{IV} from La^{III}.

Fig. 1. Elution curve for Th^{IV}-La^{III}.

Ternary separations: For resolving ternary mixtures the height of the resin bed was increased to ~10 cm.

Hg^{II}-Fe^{III}/Cu^{II}/Ga^{III}/In^{III}-Mn^{II}/Cd^{II}/Mg^{II}/Ca^{II}/Sr^{II}/Ba^{II}/Pb^{II}/La^{III}/Ce^{III} metal ions feed was prepared in 0.04 mol dm⁻³ sodium glycollate by mixing any three of the metal ions to be separated and passed through preconditioned resin column. Firstly, Hg^{II} was recovered quantitatively with ~60 cm³ of 0.04 mol dm⁻³ sodium glycollate followed by desorption of not too strongly sorbed metal ions Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ga^{III} or In^{III} with 0.12 mol dm⁻³ sodium glycollate solution. Finally, strongly retained third constituent metal ion was eluted as follows: Cd^{II}, La^{III} or Ce^{III} with ~60 cm³, Pb^{II} with ~90 cm³, and Mn^{II} with ~110 cm³ of 0.40 mol dm⁻³ sodium glycollate eluent; Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} or Ba^{II} were eluted with 4.0 mol dm⁻³ HCl. Fig. 2 shows resolution of Hg^{II}-Fe^{III}/In^{III}/Ga^{III}-Pb^{II} ternary mixtures.

Fe^{III}/Cu^{II}/Ga^{III}/In^{III}-Mn^{II}/Co^{II}/Ni^{II}/Zn^{II}/Cd^{II}/Pb^{II}/La^{III}/Ce^{III}-Sr^{II}/Ba^{II} metal ions feed was prepared in 0.12 mol dm⁻³ sodium glycollate solution. Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ga^{III} or In^{III} followed the feed effluent and were quantitatively eluted with 0.12 mol dm⁻³ sodium glycollate as described earlier. Mn^{II}/Co^{II}/Ni^{II}/Zn^{II}/Cd^{II}/Pb^{II}/La^{III}/Ce^{III} were then eluted with 0.40 mol dm⁻³ sodium glycollate followed

Fig. 2. Elution curve for Hg^{II}-Fe^{III}/In^{III}/Ga^{III}-Pb^{II}.

by the elution of very strongly sorbed Sr^{II} or Ba^{II} with 4.0 mol dm⁻³ HCl as described earlier.

Th^{IV}-Mg^{II}/Ca^{II}/Pb^{II}/La^{III}/Ce^{III}-Sr^{II}/Ba^{II} metal ions feed was prepared in 0.20 mol dm⁻³ sodium glycollate solution. Firstly, Th^{IV} was quantitatively eluted with ~100 cm³ of 0.20 mol dm⁻³ sodium glycollate followed by the elution of Mg^{II}/Ca^{II}/Pb^{II}/La^{III}/Ce^{III} with 0.40 mol dm⁻³ sodium glycollate as described earlier. Finally, Sr^{II}/Ba^{II} was eluted with 4.0 mol dm⁻³ HCl.

Thus aqueous sodium glycollate can effectively be employed for the separations of a large number of metal ions. The column kinetics and other parameters required for achieving separations were found to be favourable.

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